

Gram-Schmidt noise detection

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A previous article **[1]** explored usage of a Gram-Schmidt (GS) orthogonal companion derived from the time-reversed copy $r(t)$ of a signal $s(t)$; this companion (so referred to everywhere below) is $y(t)$:

$$y(t) = s(t) - [(s(t),s(t))/(r(t),s(t))]r(t)$$

where $(.,.)$ denotes inner product.

For an example, in OCTAVE code

```
t=0:.001:2*pi;;s=sin(t);,r=fliplr(s);,k=(s*s')/(r*s');, y=s-k*r;
```

with results plotted below; the companion is clearly $-\cos(t)$ in shape.

It turns out that even a small modicum of noise added to the sinusoid's amplitude leads to a companion barely distinguishable from noise; in effect, the Gram-Schmidt process has made the noise orthogonal to the signal! Results from the OCTAVE code

```
t=0:.001:2*pi;; nois=.001*randn(size(t));  
ns=sin(t)+nois;;nr=fliplr(ns);,nk=(ns*ns')/(nr*ns');,ny=ns-nk*nr;
```

are plotted below; the noised-up sinusoid (left panel) appears unchanged; the companion is on the right, top panel; the added noise is on the lower panel.

Companion kurtosis is 3.0382, very close to 3.0603 for the normally distributed random noise produced by the **randn** command in OCTAVE; and, of course, $\arccos(ns,ny) \approx \pi/2$. However, the companion dispersion is about 40% higher than the added noise, borne out by the images above right.

Similar results follow after noise addition to the phase of the sinusoid; the OCTAVE code this time is

```
t=0:.001:2*pi;; nois=.001*randn(size(t));  
ns=sin(t+nois);,nr=fliplr(ns);,nk=(ns*ns')/(nr*nps');,ny=ns-nk*nr;
```


The plotted outcomes above show the noised sinusoid (left panel), again seemingly unchanged; the companion (top panel right) is not entirely random though, with kurtosis = 4.5212; the inserted phase noise is in the lower panel.

The sensitivity of this method to the presence of amplitude/phase noise in periodic signals suggests an application to noise detection, and even amelioration; perhaps more usefully to performance assessment of methods claiming to de-noise signals.

[1] A. Cusmariu, <https://zenodo.org/records/14024809>